

Anthranilic Acid Hydrazide Complexes of Aluminium(III) and Titanium(IV)

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Anthranilic acid hydrazide (aaH) complexes of aluminium(III) and titanium(IV) have been synthesised by the reactions of isopropoxides and chlorides of aluminium(III) and titanium(IV) with anthranilic acid hydrazide in benzene. The complexes of the type $[Al(OPr^i)_{3-n}(aa)_n]$, $[AlCl_{3-n}(aa)_n]$ (where $n=1$ or 2), $[Ti(OPr^i)_{4-n}(aa)_n]$, $[TiCl_{4-n}(aa)_n]$ (where $n=1-3$) and (aa = anthranilic acid hydrazide anion) have been isolated. All these complexes are partially soluble in chloroform, benzene and have been characterised on the basis of elemental analysis, ir and nmr spectral studies and electrical conductance measurements.

THERE has been considerable interest in the chemistry of acid hydrazides and hydrazones because of their use in biological systems¹⁻⁴. These hydrazides and hydrazones are versatile ligands due to several potential coordination sites⁵.

Several transition metals complexes of various acid hydrazides and hydrazones have been reported^{6,7}. However, no attempt has been made to synthesise aluminium(III) and titanium(IV) complexes of acid hydrazides. Hence it was considered worthwhile to study the reactions of isopropoxides and chlorides of aluminium(III) and titanium(IV) with anthranilic acid which possesses labile protons attached to oxygen as well as nitrogen atoms. Such a study appears to be useful particularly because of the observations that 2-pyrrolidinone possessing $-NH$ and $>C=O$ group, forms adducts with titanium(IV) chloride whereas in the reactions with titanium isopropoxide, a substituted product was obtained⁸. In view of the above, anthranilic acid hydrazide was chosen whose structure is depicted below.

It is obvious from these structure that this ligand possesses one labile proton which is capable of undergoing amido-imido tautomerism.

Experimental

Glass apparatus with standard quickfit joints were used throughout the experimental work and stringent precautions were taken to exclude moisture. Benzene (AR, BDH), isopropanol (BDH) *tert*-butanol (SD'S) were dried and purified by standard method. $AlCl_3$ (BDH), $TiCl_4$ (Riedel), methyl

anthranilate (Goldsun) and hydrazine hydrate (BDH) were used as supplied. Isopropoxides of aluminium(III) and titanium(IV) were prepared by standard methods⁹⁻¹¹. Anthranilic acid hydrazide was prepared by usual method and recrystallised from chloroform.

The ir spectra were recorded on Perkin Elmer 621 spectrophotometer using nujol mulls, caesium iodide pellets or KBr pellets. The nmr spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrometer. Isopropanol was estimated by oxidimetric method¹² using $1 N K_2Cr_2O_7$ in 12.5% sulphuric acid. Chloride was estimated gravimetrically as silver chloride and nitrogen was estimated by Kjeldahl's method.

Aluminium was estimated as aluminium oxinate. Titanium was estimated as TiO_2 by direct ignition of compounds after digestion with ammonia and nitric acid in silica crucible. C and H were determined in the micro analytical laboratory of the Department of Chemistry, University of Delhi, Delhi

Reactions :

Reaction of isopropoxide of aluminium(III) with anthranilic acid hydrazide (molar ratio 1 : 1) : To a solution of $Al(OPr^i)_3$ (0.40 g ; 1.96 mmole) in benzene was added anthranilic acid hydrazide (0.30 g ; 1.96 mmole). A yellow suspension appeared at the time of addition. The resulting mixture was refluxed for about 4 hr. The isopropanol liberated was collected azeotropically and estimated¹². The excess of solvent was distilled off and the final product was dried under vacuum at $40^\circ/0.5$ mm when a white solid was obtained. Found : Isopropanol in azeotrope, 0.12 g ; Al, 8.6 ; N, 13.9. Calcd. for $[Al(OPr^i)_2(aa)]$; isopropanol in azeotrope, 0.12 g ; Al 9.1 ; N, 14.2%.

For the sake of brevity other reactions are given in Table I.

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TABLE 1—REACTIONS OF ISOPROPOXIDES OF ALUMINIUM(III) AND TITANIUM(IV)

Sl. No.	Alkoxide g (mmole)	Acid hydrazide g (mmole)	Molar ratio	Time of refluxing hr	Product and their state	Amount of isopropanol in the azeotrope (g) Found (Calcd.)	Analysis %			
							Metal	N	C	H
1.	Al(OPr ^t) ₃ 0.40 (1.95)	aaH 0.30 (1.95)	1 : 1	4	[Al(OPr ^t) ₂ aa] White solid	0.12 (0.12)	8.6 (9.1)	13.9 (14.2)	52.4 (52.9)	7.4 (7.8)
2.	Al(OPr ^t) ₃ 0.61 (2.98)	aaH 0.90 (5.96)	1 : 2	6	[Al(OPr ^t)(aa) ₂] White solid	0.35 (0.36)	6.7 (6.9)	21.3 (21.7)	—	—
3.	Ti(OPr ^t) ₄ 0.49 (1.72)	aaH 0.26 (1.72)	1 : 1	4	[Ti(OPr ^t) ₂ (aa)] Dark brown solid	0.10 (0.10)	12.6 (12.8)	11.0 (11.2)	51.0 (51.2)	7.9 (8.0)
4.	Ti(OPr ^t) ₄ 0.58 (2.03)	aaH 0.62 (4.10)	1 : 2	6	[Ti(OPr ^t) ₂ (aa) ₂] Dark brown solid	0.23 (0.24)	9.8 (10.3)	17.5 (18.0)	51.3 (51.5)	6.7 (6.8)
5.	Ti(OPr ^t) ₄ 0.31 (1.09)	aaH 0.50 (3.30)	1 : 3	12	[Ti(OPr ^t)(aa) ₃] Dark brown solid	0.19 (0.20)	8.3 (8.6)	21.7 (22.6)	51.5 (51.7)	5.9 (6.1)

TABLE 2—ALCOHOLYSIS REACTIONS OF MIXED ISOPROPOXY ACID HYDRAZIDES DERIVATIVES OF ALUMINIUM(III) AND TITANIUM(IV) WITH TERTIARY BUTANOL (EXCESS)

Sl. No.	Mixed alkoxide derivatives (g)	Alcohol	Molar ratio	Time of refluxing (hr)	Product	Amount of isopropanol in the azeotrope (g) Found (Calcd.)	Metal %
							Found (Calcd.)
1.	[Al(OPr ^t) ₂ aa] (0.22)	Bu ^t OH	1 : excess	5	[Al(OBu ^t) ₂ (aa)]	0.09 (0.09)	7.9 (8.3)
2.	[Al(OPr ^t)(aa) ₂] (0.36)	Bu ^t OH	1 : excess	3	[Al(OBu ^t)(aa) ₂]	0.05 (0.05)	6.6 (6.7)
3.	[Ti(OPr ^t) ₂ (aa)] (0.25)	Bu ^t OH	1 : excess	6	[Ti(OBu ^t) ₂ (aa)]	0.12 (0.12)	11.4 (11.5)
4.	[Ti(OPr ^t) ₂ (aa) ₂] (0.28)	Bu ^t OH	1 : excess	4	[Ti(OBu ^t) ₂ (aa) ₂]	0.07 (0.07)	9.4 (9.7)
5.	[Ti(OPr ^t)(aa) ₃] (0.40)	Bu ^t OH	1 : excess	4	[Ti(OBu ^t)(aa) ₃]	0.04 (0.04)	8.1 (8.4)

TABLE 3—REACTIONS OF CHLORIDES OF ALUMINIUM(III) AND TITANIUM(V) WITH ANTHRANILIC ACID HYDRAZIDE

Sl. No.	Metal chloride g (mmole)	Acid hydrazide g (mmole)	Molar ratio	Time of refluxing (hr)	Product	Analysis %				
						Metal Found (Calcd.)	Cl Found (Calcd.)	N Found (Calcd.)	C Found (Calcd.)	H Found (Calcd.)
1.	AlCl ₃ 0.48 (3.59)	aaH 0.54 (3.59)	1 : 1	20-22	[AlCl ₂ (aa)]	10.6 (10.8)	28.1 (28.6)	16.8 (16.9)	33.3 (33.9)	3.4 (3.6)
2.	AlCl ₃ 0.28 (2.09)	aaH 0.63 (4.17)	1 : 2	24	[AlCl(aa) ₂]	6.8 (7.4)	9.4 (9.7)	22.8 (23.1)	46.0 (46.3)	4.0 (4.9)
3.	TiCl ₄ 0.54 (2.84)	aaH 0.43 (2.84)	1 : 1	16	[TiCl ₂ (aa)]	15.1 (15.7)	34.6 (34.9)	13.2 (13.6)	27.2 (27.6)	3.0 (2.9)
4.	TiCl ₄ 0.29 (1.52)	aaH 0.46 (3.04)	1 : 2	20	[TiCl ₂ (aa) ₂]	11.2 (11.4)	16.7 (16.9)	19.7 (20.0)	39.6 (40.0)	4.0 (4.2)
5.	TiCl ₄ 0.38 (2.00)	aaH 0.91 (6.01)	1 : 3	25-26	[TiCl(aa) ₃]	8.7 (8.9)	6.5 (6.6)	23.3 (23.6)	—	—

Reaction between bis-isopropoxy aluminium(III) anthranilic acid hydrazide complex with tertiary butanol: To a solution of Al(OPr^t)₂(aa) (0.22 g) in benzene was added tertiary butanol (excess) and

the mixture was refluxed at bath temperature of 110-120°. The isopropanol liberated was fractionated azeotropically with benzene at 72-80°. The excess of solvent and tertiary butanol was removed under

reduced pressure, leaving a white solid mass. Found : Pr⁴OH in azeotrope, 0.09 g ; Al, 7.9. Calcd. for [Al(OBu^t)₃(aa)] ; Pr⁴OH in azeotrope, 0.09 g ; Al, 8.3%.

The details of other reactions are given in Table 2.

Reaction between aluminium trichloride and anthranilic acid hydrazide (aaH) (molar ratio 1 : 1) : Anthranilic acid hydrazide (0.54 g ; 3.59 mmole) was added to a suspension of aluminium trichloride (0.48 g) in benzene (~50 ml). The mixture was refluxed in an oil bath for 20-22 hr when no more hydrogen chloride gas evolved. The reaction mixture was cooled at room temperature and excess of solvent removed under reduced pressure leaving behind a white compound. Found : Al, 28.1 ; Cl, 9.6 ; N, 16.8. Calcd. for [AlCl₃(aa)] ; Al, 28.6 ; Cl, 10.8 ; N, 16.9%.

The other reactions are given in Table 3.

Results and Discussion

A systematic study of reactions of isopropoxides and chlorides of aluminium(III) and titanium(IV) with anthranilic acid hydrazide in dry benzene has been carried out in different stoichiometric ratios. The reactions proceed according to following equations :

All these complexes are white to brown in colour and are soluble in dimethylsulphoxide and dimethylformamide. Electrical conductance, measured in dimethylformamide shows them to be non-electrolyte.

Molecular weight could not be determined because of their insolubility in most of organic solvents. Only two of the isopropoxide or chloride groups are replaceable by anthranilic acid hydrazide in case of aluminium, whereas in the case of titanium three isopropoxide or chloride groups are replaced. This could be ascribed to steric hindrance or saturated coordination state of metals in these complexes, [AlX(aa)_n] and [TiX(aa)_n] (X=OPr^t or Cl). These complexes tend to decompose when heated under reduced pressure (0.01 mm).

IR spectra :

The important bands of the ligand are those which belong to amide, hydrazinic amino group vibrations. The amide group shows a number of bands due to combination of ν(C=O), ν(C-N) and ν(N-H) groups. In the spectra of ligand, the bands appearing in the regions ~ 1655-1645, 1560-1530, 1260-1250 may be assigned to amide I [ν(C=O)], amide II [ν(CN+δNH)], amide III [ν(CN+δNH)] vibrations, respectively^{13,14}. The appearance of all these bands shows that the amide group in anthra-

nilic acid hydrazide in solid state is present as such and not in its amido form. However, it may be pointed out that amide I absorbs at 1690-1650 cm⁻¹ and the lowering of amide I is due to hydrogen bonding between ketonic and amino groups of ligands as depicted below.

Accordingly, the amide group can coordinate to a metal atom through oxygen and secondary nitrogen atoms and it can also be involved in bond formation with metal atom through its imido oxygen or secondary nitrogen atom through deprotonation. The bands around 3160 and 3300 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to ν_{s,ym} NH₂ and ν_{a,s,ym} NH₂ vibrations. Additional bands at 1620-1605 and 870-865 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to δ(NH₂) and ρNH₂ vibrations.

In the aluminium(III) and titanium(IV) anthranilic acid hydrazide complexes, the amide group vibration disappears on complexation and instead a strong band is observed at ca 1610 cm⁻¹. It is likely that this band has its origin in ν(C=N) vibration which appears due to enolisation of the keto group, and the amide group

is involved in bonding with the metal atom through enolic oxygen of the amide group. The enolisation of amide group is also supported by the appearance of new bands in the region ~1580-1570 cm⁻¹ attributable to ν(NCO) vibrations. It is worth mentioning here that the ν(C=N) vibration has significant contribution from δ(NH₂) vibration which occurs in the same region of the ligands. The involvement of enolic oxygen in anthranilic acid hydrazide complexes can be attributed to greater basicity of the ligand which facilitates the enolisation of amido group¹⁵. The coordination of amino group to metal atom in aaH complexes is indicated by a lowering of ν(NH) vibration (150 cm⁻¹) and diminishing intensity or disappearance of δNH band occurring at 750 cm⁻¹. The weak bands in the region 450-400 cm⁻¹ may be due to νM-N vibration. The changes observed in ν(NH) vibration in the complexes are not very conspicuous because of the presence of hydrazinic group which counterbalances any change occurring on coordination of amido group to metal. The strong band at ~535-550 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to ν(M-O) while a peak at 1285 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to geminal dimethyl moiety of isopropoxy group¹⁶. The ν(M-Cl) absorbs at ~360-380 cm⁻¹.

NMR spectra :

The nmr spectra of the ligand show a complex multiplet at δ7.3 ppm due to phenyl ring protons, a doublet at δ(6.7-6.8) ppm assignable to protons of terminal hydrazinic amino group, doublet at δ(4.35-4.42) ppm assignable to -NH protons of -CO.NH group and finally a singlet at δ3.9 ppm, possibly due to protons of amino group.

On account of poor solubility, the nmr spectra of anthranilic acid hydrazide complexes were taken in deuterated dimethylsulphoxides. The spectra of anthranilic acid hydrazide complexes of titanium (IV) isopropoxide show a signal at δ 4.0 ppm assignable to C-NH₂ group. This downfield shift indicates that the C-NH₂ group is deshielded. This is possible due to donation of lone pair of electrons by nitrogen to the titanium atom. The signal due to -NH protons of -CO.NH group δ (4.35-4.42) ppm disappears altogether, indicating that deprotonation takes place through secondary amide nitrogen as a result of bond formation with nitrogen atom in enolic form. The position of the signal of protons due to the terminal hydrazinic group remains unperturbed ruling out the possibility of coordination of amino group. The 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 anthranilic acid hydrazide complexes of titanium(IV) show two signals at δ (1.20-1.52) ppm assignable to methyl protons of isopropoxy confirming the presence of isopropoxy group in these complexes.

Thus, it appears that anthranilic acid hydrazide acts as mononegatively charged bidentate chelating agents having coordination sites at amino and enolic oxygen atoms, respectively.

On the basis of the above studies, a polymeric structure can tentatively be assigned to these complexes. However, this may be confirmed by X-ray studies.

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